

Engineering Project Abstract

by

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'An embedded device for indoor localization in BLE networks based on a reconfigurable antenna'

This paper presents information on the resulting complete system for indoor location of objects. The resulting system uses the Fingerprinting method to determine the location, basing on the Electronically Steerable Parasitic Array Radiator (ESPAR antenna) and a smartphone serving as a mobile broadcast station. The antenna covers the space around itself, by switching configurations and receiving information about the strength of the signal received from the phone.

The diploma thesis contains, among other things, information about the antenna used in the project, the Bluetooth standard used and the implemented fingerprinting method. The process of creating an algorithm simulating the operation of the antenna and the one controlling it, as well as the problems encountered during the creation of the code was also described.

The complete system was tested at home using the telephone as a localized object. The phone's antenna was controlled by a generally available application recommended by the manufacturer of the electronic board used in the ESPAR antenna.

A series of measurements was made in various conditions in the room, resulting in confirmation of the correctness of the system operation and noting the influence of many factors on its operation. Measurement results were documented and ways to improve system performance were proposed as well.

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